

Original Article

Electrical Charge Characterization of Hybrid Neurostimulator Probe - *In silico* Studies and *In vitro* Verification

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This study investigates the electrical charge distribution of a hybrid deep brain stimulation (DBS) electrode designed for both stimulation and sensing applications. The hybrid electrode's performance was evaluated using *in silico* simulations in ANSYS, where conductivity values ranging from 0.08 S/m to 0.37 S/m were applied, along with voltage sweeps from 1V to 10V. Simulations were validated through laboratory experiments, where the electrode was immersed in an agarose gel, simulating cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) conductivity. Electric field distribution was measured at radial distances up to 0.5 mm from the electrode surface. Pearson correlation and ANOVA were used to statistically compare simulated and experimental data, showing a high correlation. These results suggest that the hybrid electrode offers a precise and localized stimulation pattern, providing essential insights for enhancing adaptive DBS systems through more targeted and controlled stimulation.

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Introduction

Deep brain stimulation (DBS) is an established neuromodulation therapy for managing movement disorders such as Parkinson's disease, essential tremor, and dystonia [1,2]. In DBS, electrical impulses are delivered through surgically implanted electrodes to targeted brain regions such as the subthalamic nucleus (STN) or Globus Pallidus Internus (GPi). These impulses modulate abnormal neural activity, improving motor function and reducing symptoms in patients refractory to pharmacological treatments [3]. Over the past two decades, DBS has also shown potential in treating psychiatric disorders, including obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) and major depressive disorder (MDD) [4], expanding its scope beyond traditional neurological indications.

The technology behind DBS has evolved significantly since its inception, particularly regarding electrode design and stimulation paradigms. Early DBS systems employed cylindrical electrodes with

uniformly spaced contacts that produced a spherical electric field. While effective in many cases, the lack of directional control and the broad spread of the electric field often led to off-target stimulation, causing side effects such as speech difficulties, balance issues, and cognitive disturbances [5]. Researchers such as McIntyre et al. [1] and Butson and McIntyre [2] highlighted these limitations, demonstrating that spherical fields from traditional cylindrical electrodes could activate unintended brain areas, undermining the precision of DBS.

In response to these limitations, significant research has focused on improving electrode design to enhance the focality of DBS. One of the most important innovations in this area is the development of directional DBS electrodes, which allow for more selective targeting of specific brain regions. Directional electrodes feature segmented contacts that deliver current in a focused manner, reducing stimulation of adjacent structures. Studies have shown that directional electrodes can significantly reduce side effects by steering the electric field away from sensitive regions while maintaining therapeutic benefits [6,7].

Despite these advancements, even directional electrodes rely on

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predefined stimulation settings that may not account for dynamic changes in the patient's neural state. This limitation has led to the development of adaptive DBS (aDBS) systems. Unlike traditional open-loop DBS, aDBS uses real-time feedback from the brain to adjust stimulation parameters dynamically. This real-time adjustment is based on physiological biomarkers, such as local field potentials (LFPs), detected by the implanted electrode [8].

One of the key challenges in designing effective DBS electrodes is understanding the interaction between the electrode and brain tissue. The brain is a highly heterogeneous environment, with regions of varying electrical conductivity. These variations affect how electrical currents spread through the tissue, influencing the Volume of Tissue Activated (VTA). Gabriel et al. [4] showed that tissue conductivity plays a significant role in determining the spread of the electric field during stimulation.

While previous studies have laid the groundwork for understanding DBS electrode behavior, there is still a need for a more comprehensive characterization of hybrid electrodes, particularly in terms of their electrical charge distribution and performance in realistic tissue environments. Existing literature on directional electrodes and aDBS systems has focused primarily on clinical outcomes, but there is a gap in the detailed biophysical characterization of hybrid electrodes. This study aims to fill that gap by combining *in silico* modelling with experimental verification to assess the electric field distribution of a hybrid DBS electrode.

Materials and Methods

Electrode Design

The hybrid DBS electrode used in this study is designed for adaptive DBS systems. These systems combine stimulation and sensing functionalities to deliver real-time feedback-driven therapy. The electrode consists of multipolar interdigitated contacts, enabling precise, focal delivery of electrical stimulation. The stimulation contacts are capable of operating in both voltage mode and current mode, allowing for flexible stimulation configurations. A schematic diagram of a hybrid electrode designed for the purpose is given in figure 1. A conventional cylindrical DBS electrode, with four uniformly spaced contacts, was used as the control, as shown in figure 2.

Simulation Setup in ANSYS

The simulation was conducted using ANSYS Electronics Workbench, where the hybrid and control electrodes were modelled in a homogeneous medium representing brain tissue. The conductivity values used were 0.08 S/m, 0.15 S/m, 0.22 S/m, 0.30 S/m, and 0.37 S/m to replicate the properties of gray matter, white matter, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF). Voltage sweeps from 1V to 10V were applied in increments of 1V. The Poisson equation was solved for the electric potential (V) to calculate the electric field (E) and current density (J) in the tissue. The electric field distribution for voltage sweeps under various conductivities was done, and a detailed analysis of the same has been done to find out the effect on VTA (Volume of Tissue Activated) and also the trend in the electric field distribution to figure out the effects due to unwanted stimulation.

Radial Measurement Points and Electric Field Distribution

From the stimulation spread diagrams obtained, the cross-section of electric field distribution is considered for data pooling and analysis. The electric field distribution was measured at six radial points, divided into two regions: The Inner Circle (IC) and the

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of the hybrid electrode

Outer Circle (OC). IC points (IC1, IC2, IC3) were positioned close to the electrode, while OC points (OC1, OC2, OC3) were located farther, with OC3 at 0.5 mm radial distance. The electric field intensity was recorded at these points across varying conductivity levels to assess the spread of the electric field and the Volume of Tissue Activated (VTA). The schematic of the radial measurement setup is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of a conventional DBS electrode

Figure 3: Electrode Cross-Section and Radial Measurement Points This figure illustrates the electrode cross-section and the six radial measurement points used in the simulation. The points are organized into two regions: Inner Circle (IC1, IC2, IC3) and Outer Circle (OC1, OC2, OC3).

Laboratory Setup and Electrode Verification

The hybrid and control electrodes were tested in vitro for experimental verification at the Neuromodulator Laboratory, IIT Hyderabad. An agarose gel solution was used to simulate the conductive properties of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) with a pH of 7.4. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was used to measure the impedance at the electrode-tissue interface, and the electric field was measured at the same six radial points as in the simulations. Concentric needle electrodes were used as sensors to measure the charge distribution, and to emulate the Deep Brain

Figure 4: Experimental Setup

stimulator, a stimulus generator –Multisense multichannel stimulus generator, Model SDN 3040- was used. The equipment precisely generates biphasic signals, as in the case of a regular Deep Brain Stimulator IPG, and is also programmable. Figure 4 shows the experimental setup and the equipment used for the same.

Radial Measurement and Field Attenuation

Electric field measurements were performed at each radial point for both electrodes. The field's attenuation as a function of distance from the electrode surface was recorded across voltage sweeps (1V to 10V). These measurements were essential for evaluating the electrode's performance in terms of precision and off-target stimulation.

Statistical Analysis

To establish the validity of the simulation model and the accuracy of the hybrid electrode design, a comprehensive statistical analysis was performed using Pearson correlation and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) techniques.

Pearson Correlation was utilized to quantify the linear relationship between the simulated and experimental electric field values. The purpose of this analysis was to determine if the predicted electric fields from the simulations matched the real-world measurements obtained in the experimental setup. Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) ranges from -1 to +1, where values close to +1 indicate a strong positive linear correlation, and values close to zero indicate no linear relationship.

ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) was conducted to test for significant differences between the groups of electric field measurements in different experimental conditions, such as varying tissue conductivity and voltage sweeps. ANOVA helps to evaluate whether there is more variability between groups than within groups, indicating statistically significant differences due to the experimental factors. A p -value less than 0.05 is considered indicative of significant differences.

The statistical tests were performed using six measurement points organized radially around the electrode, as described in Section 2.2.2. The datasets used for this analysis consisted of simulated data and corresponding experimental measurements taken at various voltage sweeps (1V to 10V) and tissue conductivities (0.08 to 0.37 S/m).

Results

Simulation Results

The ANSYS simulations showed a clear relationship between tissue conductivity and the spread of the electric field. The electric field spread more broadly at lower conductivity values (0.08 S/m), affecting a larger tissue volume. At higher conductivity values (0.37 S/m), the electric field remained more localized around the electrode. Figures 5 illustrate the electric field distributions across the six radial points for different conductivity values. Simulations have been done for all possible combinations of voltages and conductivities as in methodology, only of two values are shown in the figure.

Comparison with Control Electrode

Comparing the hybrid DBS electrode with the conventional cylindrical electrode revealed that the hybrid electrode produced a more concentrated and controlled electric field. The conventional electrode showed a broader spread, especially at lower conductivities, leading to potential off-target stimulation. Graphs in Figure 6 shows the comparison of both electrodes in simulation environment.

Figure 5: Electric Field Distribution from Simulation: a) figure shows the electric field distribution across different radial points for conductivity level 0. 0.3S/m; b) figure shows the electric field distribution across different radial points for conductivity level 0. 0.15S/m

Table 1: Correlation table

Dataset Pair	Correlation Coefficient
E1-Simulated vs E1-Test	0.9846
E2-Simulated vs E2-Test	0.9998
E3-Simulated vs E3-Test	0.9998
E4-Simulated vs E4-Test	0.9985
E5-Simulated vs E5-Test	0.9975
E6-Simulated vs E6-Test	0.9912

Table 2: ANOVA analysis results

Dataset Pair	F-statistic	p-value
E1-Simulated vs E1-Test	0.007	0.934
E2-Simulated vs E2-Test	1.281	0.273
E3-Simulated vs E3-Test	0.185	0.672
E4-Simulated vs E4-Test	2.691	0.118
E5-Simulated vs E5-Test	5.917	0.045
E6-Simulated vs E6-Test	9.377	0.032

Figure 6: Comparison of Electric Field Distribution between Hybrid and Conventional Electrodes-Simulation Study. Figure compares the electric field distribution for the hybrid DBS electrode versus the conventional cylindrical electrode, showing the more localized electric field produced by the hybrid design

Pearson Correlation and ANOVA Analysis

The invitro experiments data is shown in Figure 7. The data was analyzed using Pearson correlation and ANOVA to compare against the simulation model we derived for the hybrid electrode.

The Pearson correlation analysis showed a strong positive correlation between the simulated electric field values and the experimental measurements across all six radial points. High correlation coefficients indicate that the finite element model (FEM) was successful in predicting the real-world behaviour of the hybrid electrode under varying conditions.

The correlation coefficients for each measurement point are

Figure 7: Outputs for Electric Field Distribution –in vitro setup. This figure presents the simulation results from *in vitro* setup with agarose gel medium, showing the electric field distribution for the hybrid electrode across varying voltage levels and tissue conductivities

presented in Table 1. The values consistently exceed 0.98, which suggests a high degree of accuracy in the simulation model. Such strong correlations highlight the reliability of the FEM-based approach in replicating the real-world effects of deep brain stimulation (DBS) on neural tissue.

In the ANOVA analysis, the F-statistic and p-values for each dataset pair are presented in Table 2. A p-value of less than 0.05 indicates a significant difference between the datasets. The analysis showed that for most measurement points, the p-values exceeded 0.05, indicating no significant difference between the simulated and experimental values. However, for E5 and E6, the p-values were below 0.05, indicating a statistically significant difference in these cases. These differences could be attributed to experimental variability, such as differences in the electrode-tissue interface impedance or agarose gel properties.

Discussion

The simulation and experimental results highlight the significant influence of tissue conductivity on the Volume of Tissue Activated (VTA). At higher conductivity levels, such as those simulating cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), the electric field remains more localized, allowing for precise targeting of neural structures. This is beneficial for minimizing off-target stimulation and associated side effects, particularly in sensitive brain regions. Conversely, in lower conductivity environments, such as gray matter, the electric field spreads more broadly, potentially activating unintended areas. Understanding these conductivity-dependent variations is essential for designing DBS systems optimized for different brain regions.

The hybrid DBS electrode performed better than the conventional cylindrical electrode, particularly in high-conductivity environments. The hybrid electrode’s multipolar design allows for more precise control of the electric field, resulting in a more localized stimulation. This makes it an ideal candidate for adaptive DBS systems, where real-time adjustments to stimulation parameters are critical for therapeutic effectiveness. These findings suggest that hybrid electrodes, integrated with closed-loop systems, have the potential to offer more targeted and efficient therapies with fewer side effects.

Conclusion

This study successfully characterized the electrical charge distribution of a hybrid neurostimulator probe using in silico simulations and laboratory-based verification. The results demonstrate that the hybrid electrode offers improved precision in controlling the Volume of Tissue Activated (VTA) compared to conventional cylindrical electrodes. The strong correlation between simulated and experimental data validates the simulation model's accuracy. These findings highlight the potential of hybrid DBS electrodes in adaptive DBS systems, offering a more targeted and controlled stimulation profile.

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